

A taxonomical survey of 5G and 6G security and privacy issues

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Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances, 2023, 14(03), 042–060

Publication history: Received on 31 January 2023; revised on 10 March 2023; accepted on 12 March 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gjeta.2023.14.3.0047>

Abstract

Extensive research has been done on 5G and 6G security challenges. It has been shown that these challenges have the potential of affecting cross board 5G and 6G ecosystems such as technologies, services and applications. The perspective of the currently identified security challenges vary depending on the researcher's area of concern. This survey generated a consolidated source of information on the taxonomy of 5G and 6G ecosystem security challenges necessary for addressing both pre and post security issues to be encountered upon 5G and 6G implementation.

Keywords: Attacks; Privacy; Security; 5G; 6G; Networks

1. Introduction

Wireless technology has been widely adopted due to its ability to transcend terrestrial obstacles. This technology has advanced tremendously since the first generation to the current yet to be deployed 6G. 5G, which is a predecessor of 6G provide higher capacities, higher data rates, lower latency, massive device connectivity, lower cost, and better consistent quality of service than 4G networks [1]. 5G networks are expected to deliver extensive variety of services comprising enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable and low-latency communications (uRLLC), and massive type of communications (mMTC) [2]. The emergence of the internet of things (IoT) has led to the need for higher rates in the wireless networks evolution. Although 5G has proved an evolutionary generation for connecting, supporting IoT networks and providing new services, as well as offering significant improvement over the existing systems, it will not be able to fulfill the demands of future emerging intelligent and automation systems [3]. The unprecedented growth of new IoT services is on-going to consider a broad range of applications, such as extended reality (XR) services, telemedicine, haptics, drones, brain computer interfaces, and connected autonomous systems [4]. The 6G on its part will be driven by emerging technologies, services and applications. Networking and communication scientific community envisage that 6G will be driven entirely by network orchestration and management [5], [6], [7]. 6G will be characterized by the following factors [8]:

- AI integrated communication
- Tactile Internet
- High energy efficiency
- Low backhaul and access network congestion
- Enhanced data security
- As concerns related to the migration implementation of 6G are being addressed [9], there is also need to consider emerging vulnerabilities and threats that may affect 6G security [9].

The contributions of this paper include the following:

- A 5G brief review and a summary background on 6G technologies, services and applications are provided.

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- A summary of security issues across 6G ecosystem (technologies, services and applications) is given.
- A summary of solutions for 6G ecosystem (technologies, services and applications) security issues is provided.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses 5G and 6G networks in general, while Section 3 presents the various 6G ecosystem technologies. On the other hand, Section 4 discusses the general 6G services, while Section 5 presents specific 6G applications. Similarly, Section 6 discusses the general wireless technology security pathway, while Section 7 presents the 6G Security threats and vulnerabilities. On the other hand, Section 8 discusses the various solutions to 6G threats and vulnerabilities. Finally, Section 9 concludes the paper and offers some future research work. Table 1 presents the acronyms used throughout this paper.

Table 1 Acronyms

5G	Fifth Generation
6G	Sixth Generation
eMBB	Enhanced mobile Broadband
uRLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency communication
mMTC	Massive Machine-Type Communication
IoT	Internet of Things
XR	Extended reality
AI	Artificial Intelligence
THz	Sub-Terahertz
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicles
3 D	Three-Dimensional
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple -Output
FSO	Free space Optical
MBRLLC	Mobile broadband reliable low-latency communication
mURLLC	Massive URLLC
HCS	Human-centric services
MPS	Multi-protocol SerDes
3CLS	Convergence of communication, control, localization and sensing
WET	Wireless Energy Transfer
AR	Augmented Reality
VR	Virtual Reality
MR	Mixed Reality
CAV	Connected autonomous vehicles
QoL	Quality of Life
IWD	Intelligent wearable devices
IloMT	Intelligent Internet of Medical of Things
H2H	Hospital-to-Home
DLT	Distributed ledger technology
NFV	Network function virtualization
SDN	Software defined networking

API	Application programming interfaces
DoS	Denial of service
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence/Machine Language
E2eE	End to End
SLA	Service level agreement
VM	Virtual machine
VLC	Visible Light Communication
VPN	Virtual private networks
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security

2. The 5G and 6G Networks

An increase in wireless data traffic volume and magnitude of connected things is expected to leap to hundredfold of equipment in a given cubic meter. Data hungry applications such as sending holographic videos require a spectrum bandwidth that is currently unavailable in the mm-wave spectrum. This is a challenge on an area of spatial spectral efficiency and the needed frequency spectrum bands for connectivity hence a need for a broader radio frequency spectrum bands for connectivity. It is expected that this will be addressed by broader radio frequency spectrum bandwidth which can only be found at the sub-terahertz (THz) and THz bands [10]. The recent upsurge of diversified mobile applications, especially those supported by Artificial intelligence (AI) technology is spurring heated discussions on the future evolution of the wireless communication [11], [12]. 5G applications are considered under three services, eMBB, URLLC, mMTC [13] as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2 5G service types

Research	Service type	Focus Area
[13]	Enhanced mobile Broadband (eMBB)	eMBB applications prioritizes high throughput, capacity and spectral efficiency
	Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency communication (URLLC)	High reliability low latency
	Machine- Type Communication mMTC	Energy efficiency an massive connectivity

3. 6G Ecosystem Technologies

6G can be framed into one big vision statement of ubiquitous wireless intelligence. It will experience unparalleled revolution that will re-shape the wireless evolution from “connected things” to “connected intelligence.” 6G will support ubiquitous services from core to the end devices of the network. AI will be the driving force in designing and optimizing 6G architectures, protocols and operations [14],[15]. Although AI has not been used in the previous generations of mobile technologies it will be essential in the development of 6G in order to automate resources management [16] and improve air interface algorithms [17]. 6G will satisfy future expectations of IoT applications and overcome the restrictions of 5G networks [18], [19]. 6G will be able to “connect everything, provide full dimensional wireless coverage, integrate all functions, including sensing, communication, computing, caching, control, positioning, radar, navigation, and imaging to support full-vertical applications”[20].Major technology trends promoting the development of 6G include; terahertz: essential to implement mobile networks that can be integrated with sensing to provide optimized transport management, a need for three-dimensional vertical networks to integrate satellite and cellular communication to support seamless connections of (UAV’s), artificial intelligence to enhance network performance and decrease the computational complexity of network operation, green and sustainable design a critical requirement of mobile networks which promotes development of 6G [21].Table 3 below represents some of technologies identified by previous researchers that will that are being considered for 6G.

Table 3 6G technologies

Authors	Research contributions	Focus Area
		Technologies
[22]-[25]	Discusses the emergence of the optical wireless technology along radio frequency and its support to upcoming 6G applications	Optical wireless communication systems
[26] [28]-[31]	Focuses on how the bandwidth [27] can be increased so that it's able to support the upcoming 6G technology.	Terahertz Band
[32] [33] [35] [36] [37]	Brings to attention the importance of AI [34] and its role as a key enabler towards the roll out of emerging 6G technologies	Artificial Intelligence
[38] [39]	Discusses about integration of ground and airborne networks to users in the vertical extension.	3D Networking
[40]	Explains on the importance of unsupervised learning which will play a key role against cyber attacks [41]	Quantum communication
[42] [43]	Contributes to how mMIMO technique can be used to improve spectral efficiency	Massive MIMO
[44]	Duels on how devices without batteries will be supported in 6G connections. It also focuses on lengthening the lifetime of the battery charging wireless systems.	Integration of wireless information and energy transfer
[45]	Discusses on how to handle and manage big data.	Big data analytics
[46] [47] [49]-[52]	Discusses on management of massive data [48] through distributed ledger technology	Block chain
[53] [54]	Enlightens on big data computing	Mobile edge computing
Author(s)	Research contributions	Focus area
		Medium of communication
[55] [57] [58]	Focuses on how to integrate terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks to extend wireless [56] coverage.	Integrated space terrestrial network
[8]	Identifies the limitations of optical fibre links and the strengths of the FSO front haul/backhaul. The limitation areas of usage and the application of FSO front haul/backhaul are also explained.	FSO front haul/backhaul network
[59]	Discusses about the benefits of having UAV's as compared to fixed base stations	Unmanned aerial vehicles/Drones

4. 6G Services

5G Compatible application will be central to the emerging 6G on a broader scale. Several emerging fast paced solutions are expected to be deployed with 6G technologies. 6G services will redefine those from the 5G by morphing the classic URLLC, eMBB with new services in the Table 4 below [60].

Table 4 6G services

Author(s)	Service type	Performance indicators
[4]	MBRLLC	-Stringent rate-reliability-latency requirements -Energy efficiency -Rate-reliability-latency in mobile environment
	mURLLC	-Ultra high reliability -Massive connectivity -Massive reliability Scalable URLLC
	HCS (Human-centric services)	-QOPE capturing wireless metrics as well as human and physical factors
	MPS	-Control stability Computing latency -Localization accuracy -Sensing and mapping accuracy. -Latency and reliability for communications -energy
	Multipurpose 3CLS.	-Deliver 3CL services -Provide wireless energy transfer (WET) to smart devices.
[60]	Network Slicing	-Supports a range of service requirements

5. 6G Applications

The emergence of new applications that will define 6G is taking shape. These applications will drastically shape the human society of 2030's and beyond. The general performance expectations and security requirements will become more complicated with the emergence of very capable ubiquitous threat matrix [9]. Different author have addressed a number of these emerging applications. Some other applications cut across their literature while others are individualized. These applications have been summarized in Table 5 below to give an overview of how 6G will be useful.

Table 5 6G Applications

Author(s)	Application	Purpose
[61] [62]	UAV Based mobility (UAV)	UAV'S [63] will be used in new cases such a s passenger taxi, automated logistics and military operations.
[64] [65]	Holographic tele-presence	Will project realistic three dimensional (3D) images of distant people and objects with a high level of realism rivalling physical presence.
[66] [67]	Extended reality	Extended reality (XR) is a term used to refer all real and virtual combined environments which cover

		Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), Mixed Reality (MR and everything in between.
[68] [69]	Connected autonomous vehicles (CAV)	Will support vehicle requirements e.g. driver-less taxi and driver-less public transport
[70]	Smart Grid 2.0	Smart Grid 2.0 will offer features such as automated meter data analysis, distribution grid [71] management automation and reliable electric power delivery with self-healing capabilities
[72]	Industry 5.0	This industrial revolution will enable people to work alongside robots and smart machines to add a personal touch to the industry
[73] [74]	Intelligent health care	In a few years, AI -driven intelligent healthcare will be developed based on various new methodologies including Quality of Life (QoL), Intelligent wearable devices (IWD), Intelligent Internet of Medical of Things (IIoMT), Hospital-to-Home (H2H services and novel business models.
[75] [76]	Digital Twin	This is a novel industrial control and automation systems concept. A digital twin is defined as a digital or virtual copy of a physical object, an asset or a product.
[77]	Distributed ledger technology (DLT)	Block chain provide the advantage of disintermediation, immutability, non-repudiation, proof of governance, integrity and pseudonymity [78] are important to enable different services in a trusted and secure manner.
[79] [80]	Haptic communication	Enables expression through a sense of touch
[81]	Multi-dimensional reality	Enable 3D games or multi-dimensional video that interact with all five sense organs of the body to create an illusion of real-world by combining VR and AR to render a true gaming experience
[82] [83]	Tactile internet	Enables transmission of touch, feelings (sense) along with audio and video or other forms of responses.
[84] [86]	Wireless brain computer	Wireless [85] brain computer is expected to introduce new use-cases that need 6G connectivity. The imminent use-cases are expected to enable brain-controlled movie input to fully -fledged multi brain-controlled cinema

6. Wireless technology security pathway

Security in wireless technology is an evolving target. Early technologies (1G, 2G, 3G) encountered security challenges that included cloning, illegal physical attacks, eavesdropping, encryption issues, authentication, authorization problems, and privacy issues [87]. 4G networks were defined by security challenges that included MEDIA access control (MAC) layer security threats (denial of service attacks, eavesdropping, replay attacks), and malware applications (viruses, hardware tampering) [34]. 5G Security and privacy threats target access, backhaul, and core networks [9]. They include cyber ware and critical infrastructure threats, Network function virtualization (NFV), software-defined networking (SDN), related threats and cloud computing related threats [88]. Some of the security threats due to SDN are critical due to the exposure of Application programming interfaces (API's) to unintended software, inception of Open Flow, centralized network control as a result of DOS attacks [89]. Although there are many 6G vision papers, only a handful of

surveys have been released with key focus on 6G security and privacy issues. Table 6 summarizes some of the security issues in 5G networks.

Table 6 5G security threats and vulnerabilities

	Software-Defined Networking (SDN)
Author(s)	Threat/Vulnerability
[90]	Attacks on SDN controller
	Attacks on northbound and southbound interfaces
	Inherent vulnerabilities [91] of platforms used to deploy SDN controllers/applications
	Network Function Virtualization (NFV)
Research	Threat/Vulnerability
[92]	Attacks targeting virtual machines (VM)
	Virtual network functions (VNF), hypervisor, VNF manager, NFV Orchestrator
	Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)
[93]	Physical security threats
	Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS)
	Man- in the middle attack

7. 6G Security threats and vulnerabilities

The implementation of the above technologies vary with some being an advancement of the preceding technology 5G while others are specifically under development to be used once the implementation of 6G takes place. Security is key for the success of any technology including 6G. Some of the security threats and vulnerabilities are inherent due to the previous technologies while others will be exploits of the new technology 6G due to technological limitations, flaws and shortcomings. These security issues affect all the pillars of 6G technology that include technology, applications and services. This work summarizes these security vulnerabilities and threats to the 6G technology as in the Table 7 below.

Table 7 6G security threats and vulnerabilities

	Block Chain	
Author(s)	Threat/Vulnerability	Impact
[94] [95]	Double spending attack	User spending a single token multiple times
[96]	Re-entrance attacks	Occurs when a smart contract invokes another smart contract iterative
[97]	Sybil attacks	Attacker or a group of attackers try to hijack [98] the block chain peer network by conceiving fake identities
[99]-[102]	Privacy leakages	Leakage of transaction data privacy Leakage of smart contract logic privacy Leakage of user contracts

		Leakage of user privacy Privacy leakage while execution of smart contracts Revealing of information to competitors
	Quantum computing	
Author(s)	Threat/Vulnerability	Impact
[37]	Challenge of having device independent post quantum cryptography	Difficulty in providing solutions to prevent quantum based attacks
	Artificial intelligence/ Machine learning	
Author(s)	Threat/Vulnerability	Impact
[103]	Training phase poisoning attacks	The attacker can tamper the training data by injecting carefully crafted malicious [104] sample to influence the outcome of the learning method.
[105] [106]	Test phase evasion attacks	Attempts to circumvent the learned model by introducing disorders to the test data.
[37]	Comprise of AI frameworks	Exploits vulnerabilities artefacts or traditional attack vectors towards software, firmware and hardware elements
[37]	AI/ML API based attacks	An adversary queries and attack an API of a ML model to obtain predictions on input feature vectors which may lead to model inversion (Training data recovery), model extraction (model architecture comprising model confidentiality revelation) and membership inference (exploit model output to predict on training data and ML model) attacks.
	Terahertz technology	
Author(s)	Threat/Vulnerability	Impact
[37]	eavesdropping, and access control attacks	Exposes transmitted data transmitted to threats and vulnerabilities.
	Optical wireless communication (visible light communication technology)	
Author(s)	Threat/Vulnerability	Impact
[107]	Prone to eavesdropping attacks	Comprises confidentiality
	Open API's Security threats	
Author(s)	Threat/Vulnerability	Impact
[108] [109] [111]	Parameter attacks	Improperly validated [110] parameters may lead to injection attacks on cross-domain data services -Data injection, data manipulation and logic corruption -manipulating network topology data to insert fake links, malicious nodes. -Continuous injection of false parameters may lead DoS attack to make data services unresponsive

	Identity attacks	-Exploit laws in authentication and authorization -Extraction of API keys and using them as credentials -Attack insecure E2eE domain orchestration service to change configurations to fail SLA's, create new instances demanding more resources to exhaust the network
	Man-in the middle attack	-obtain information from unencrypted transmission of API messages between the API consumer and provider. -Interception of API messages and revealing confidential information
	Dos/DDoS attacks	-Make an API out of order by submerging it with massive amount of requests.
	Closed loop Automation	
Author(s)	Threat/Vulnerability	Impact
[108] [109]	Dos attacks	Fake heavy load on VNFs to increase the capacity of VM, which may lead to DoS
[111] [112]	Man-in-the-middle attacks	-Triggering a fake event and intercept the domain control messages to reroute traffic via a malicious switch
	Deception on attacks	Intends to tamper transmitted data
	Intent-Based Interfaces	
[108], [113]-[115]	Information Exposure	Intercepting information of intents by an unauthorized entities to compromise system security objectives(e.g. , privacy, confidentiality [116] .This may lead to the launch of other attacks
	Undesirable configuration	Changing the mapping from intent to action. Setting the security level from ``High'' to``Low''
	Abnormal behaviours	Malformed intent could change the behaviour, causing network outage
	Mal-informed intent	Changing the intent reduce the service quality

8. Solutions to 6G threats and vulnerabilities

There exist solutions that have been outlined that will address threats and vulnerabilities prone to 6G. A summary of these solutions is outlined in Table 8 below.

Table 8 Solutions to 6G threats and vulnerabilities

Blockchain		
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[117] [118]	2017 2018	Proper validation of correct functionality of smart contracts by identifying semantic flaws
[119] [120] [121]	2018 2018 2018	Using security check tools
[122] [123]		Pre-forming formal verification [124]
[37]		Proper access control

[125]	2010	Privacy by design and TEE
[126]	2009	
[127]	2019	
[128]	2018	
[129]	2021	Selecting proper block chain/DLT
	Quantum computing	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[130]	2020	Post quantum cryptographic primitives (Lattice-based, hash-based and multivariate-based cryptography)
	Artificial intelligence/machine learning	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[131]	2017	Adversarial training injects perturbed examples similar to attacks [132] into training data to increase robustness
[133]	2019	Defensive distillation
[134]	2020	Against poisoning attacks in the training phase block chain provides a distributed, transparent and secure data sharing framework perspective
[135]	2019	Moving target defence
[136]	2019	
[137]	2020	Input validation [138]
[37]		Control of information provided by ML API's to the algorithm to prevent them
[139]	2018	Addition of noise to ML prediction
	Terahertz technology	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[140]	2019	Channel characterization of the backscatter
[141]	2017	-Sharing data transmission over multiple paths -Secure key exchange
[142]	2020	performing authentication at the physical layer in vivo nano-networks at THz frequencies
	Optical wireless communication (visible light communication technology)	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[143]	2019	Using linear precoding to enhance the performance of multiple-input multiple output (MIMO) VLC system.
[144]	2020	Exploitation of PLS
	Open API's Security threats	
	Parameter attacks	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution

[108] [109] [111]	2020, 2020 2021	-Input validation and user authentication. -Access control and rate limiting
	Identity attacks	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [109] [111]	2020, 2020 2021	-Authentication (Signed JWT tokens, OpenID connect) -Authorization(Role based Access control, Attribute based access control list)
	Man-in the middle attack	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [109] [111]	2020, 2020 2021	-Use secure encrypted communication -Use of VPNs (e.g. IPsec, SSL/TLS and HIP)
	Dos/DDoS attacks	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [109] [111]	2020 2020 2021	-Throttling/rate limiting the usage of APIs -Deployment of API gateways and micro gateways -AI based API security for proactive monitoring
	Closed loop Automation	
	Dos attacks	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [109] [111] [112]	2020 2020 2021 2020	-Throttling /rate limiting on resources for VMS -AI based resources level prediction
	Man-in-the-middle attacks	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [109] [111] [112]	2020 2020 2021 2020	-Use secure encrypted communication -Use of VPN's(e.g. IPsec, SSL/TLS and HIP)
	Deception on attacks	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [109] [111] [112]	2020 2020 2021 2020	- Use Integrity validation mechanisms (e.g. Block chain)
	Intent-Based Interfaces	
	Information Exposure	

Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [113] [114] [115]	2020 2020 2016 2020	-Authentication between intent producer and consumer (Signed JWT tokens, OpenID connect) -Controlled access via authorization controls (Role based Access Control, OAuth 2.0) -Secure communication via transport protocols (TLS 1.2)
	Undesirable configuration	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [113] [114] [115]	2020 2020 2016 2020	-Input validation via user authentication
	Abnormal behaviours	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [113] [114] [115]	2020, 2020 2016 2020	-AI Based proactive for abnormality detection
	Mal-informed intent	
Author(s)	Publication Year	Solution
[108] [113] [114] [115]	2020 2020 2016 2020	Intent format validation

9. Conclusion

This paper has provided an overview of consolidated current existing information related to 6G and 5G networks. Due to massive number of devices that will rely on network connectivity and the need towards using advanced technology in solving problems, this paper provides a useful source of reference. All key aspects that include technology, services, applications security in 5G and 6G proposed solutions have been considered. Since 6G is a technology yet to be rolled out, further studies should be focused towards specific areas of the technology because of 6G complexity and massive ecosystem.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

I would like to appreciate the members of the ICT department for the assistance offered during the drafting and writing of this manuscript.

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